

Regional Assessment of the Seagrass *Ruppia didyma* Sw. ex Wikstr. in the Tropical Atlantic Seagrass Bioregion (Bioregion 2) for the IUCN Red List ^{1,2}

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PLANTAE - TRACHEOPHYTA - LILIOPSIDA - ALISMATALES - RUPPIACEAE - *Ruppia* - *didyma*

Common Names:

Synonyms: *Ruppia maritima* L. (misapplied), *Ruppia anomala* Ostenf.

Taxonomic Note:

Some authors considered *Ruppia didyma* a synonym of *R. maritima* (Ascherson & Graebner, 1907; Grisebach, 1864). The species was redescribed as a separate species by Novelo (1991), and available molecular data indicate that it is more closely related to the SE Asian *Ruppia brevipedunculata* than to *R. maritima* and *R. mexicana*, the other two species of the *Ruppia maritima* complex found in the Tropical Atlantic (Triest et al., 2018; unpublished data Frade, Serrão & van Tussenbroek). The most obvious difference from these two species is that the podogyne of two fruits are fused instead of each fruit having its own podogyne (den Hartog et al., 2016; Novelo, 1991). The taxonomy of the genus *Ruppia* in the Americas remains problematic (den Hartog et al., 2016; den Hartog & Triest, 2020), and requires further research.

Red List Status
VU Vulnerable, (IUCN version 16)
B2ab(i,ii,iii,iv)
Extent of Occurrence (EOO)= 1,988,955 km ² ; Area of occupancy (AOO) = 1,400 km ²

¹ This regional assessment also constitutes the global assessment for this species, given that its global distribution is limited to the Tropical Atlantic Seagrass Bioregion.

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Assessment Information

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Time period assessed: up to 2020

Assessment Rationale

Ruppia didyma is known from a few locations in the Caribbean, Mexico, and Venezuela. It inhabits small waterbodies with clear, hypersaline water, generally near mangroves. The species has a small AOO (1400 km² or less), and occurs in 13-16 subpopulations that are likely to be severely fragmented given their disperse distribution and the large distance between them. It has been reported from Guadeloupe, Puerto Rico and Saint Barthelemy, but there are no recent records from these islands. The only known location in Puerto Rico (Guánica Lagoon) has since been drained, and coastal wetlands in both Saint Barthelemy and Guadeloupe face continuing degradation from coastal development. The species is assessed here for the first time and it is categorized as Vulnerable (VU B2ab(i,ii,iii,iv)). Further research is needed on the current distribution, ecology, population trends and conservation needs of this species.

Distribution

Geographic Range

Ruppia didyma was originally described from specimens collected in Saint Barthelemy (Wikström, 1825), The species has been collected few times since, with records from Puerto Rico (Ostenfeld, 1915), Guadeloupe (Novelo, 1991), Mexico (Atlantic and Pacific) (Novelo, 1991) and Venezuela (Villarreal et al., 2014; Wingfield, 2012). The exact collection site in Saint Barthelemy and Guadeloupe is unknown and there are no recent records from the Caribbean.

In Puerto Rico, *R. didyma* was collected in Guánica Lagoon prior to 1915 (Ostenfeld, 1915), but has not been found since (Acevedo-Rodríguez & Strong, 2005). Guánica lagoon was drained in 1955 (Viqueira Rios et al., 2012) and the species may be locally extinct. In Saint Barthelemy and Guadeloupe, mangrove-dominated wetlands face continuing degradation from coastal development (Ellison & Farnsworth, 1996; Jadot, 2016).

In Mexico, *R. didyma* has been reported from both the Pacific and Atlantic coasts (Novelo, 1991; Solomon & Stimmel, 2021; unpublished data van Tussenbroek). It occurs in the states of Sinaloa (Huizache-Caimanero Lagoon), Nayarit (Santiago Ixcuintla municipality), Jalisco (La Huerta municipality), Colima (Cuyutlán Lagoon), Oaxaca (Salinas del Marqués), Campeche (Calkiní municipality), Yucatan (Dzemul, Progreso and Tizimín municipalities) and Quintana Roo (Cenote Cristalino and Cenote Eden). The natural conditions of the hypersaline lagoons at N-Yucatán are deteriorating due to exploitations of salt pans (Van Tussenbroek, personal observation).

In Venezuela, *R. didyma* has been reported from La Vela de Coro, Falcón state (Wingfield, 2012), and Isla de Zapara, Zulia state (Villarreal et al., 2014).

The species has been recorded historically in 16 locations, but there are no recent records from three of these (Guadeloupe, Saint Barthelemy, and Puerto Rico) and the species is likely locally extinct in one of them (Puerto Rico). The historical Extent of Occurrence (EOO) and Area of Occurrence (AOO) were determined using GeoCAT (Bachman et al., 2011). Historical Extent of Occurrence (EOO) is estimated to have been 3255194 km², considering all known occurrences. However, the only known locality in Puerto Rico has since been destroyed and there are no recent records from elsewhere in the Caribbean. EOO is 1988955 km² if only the recent confirmed records from Mexico and Venezuela are included.

Historical Area of Occurrence (AOO) is estimated to have as 1700 km², considering all known occurrences and conservatively using a 10 km² grid to account for uncertainties in the location, as many historical records lack detailed descriptions of the collection site. However, the AOO is likely to have declined with the destruction of Guánica Lagoon, Puerto Rico and ongoing habitat degradation elsewhere in the Caribbean and Mexico.

Extent of Occurrence (EOO)

Estimated extent of occurrence (EOO)- in km²: 1988955-3255194

Continuing decline in extent of occupancy (EOO)	Qualifier	Justification
Yes	Suspected	Single known locality in Puerto Rico was drained. No recent records from the Caribbean, where habitat is heavily degraded.

Extreme fluctuations in extent of occurrence (EOO): No.

Locations Information

Number of Locations: 16 locations, but there are no recent records from 3 of these (Guadeloupe, Saint Barthelemy, and Puerto Rico) and 1 is likely extirpated (Puerto Rico).

Continuing decline in number of locations	Qualifier	Justification
Yes	Suspected	Single locality known in Puerto Rico was drained. No recent records from the Caribbean, where habitat is heavily degraded.

Extreme fluctuations in the number of locations: No.

Elevation / Depth / Depth Zones

Depth Lower Limit (in metres below sea level): 1

Depth Upper Limit (in metres below sea level): 0

Depth Zone: Shallow photic (0-50m)

Occurrence

Countries of Occurrence

Country	Presence	Origin	Formerly Bred	Seasonality
Puerto Rico	Possibly Extinct	Native	-	Resident
Saint Bathélemy	Possibly Extinct	Native	-	Resident
Guadeloupe	Possibly Extinct	Native	-	Resident
Mexico	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Venezuela	Extant	Native	-	Resident

FAO Area Occurrence

	Presence	Origin	Formerly Bred	Seasonality
31. Atlantic - western central	Extant	Native	-	Resident

Map Status

Map Status	How the map was created, including data sources/methods used:	Please state reason for map not available:	Data Sensitive?	Justification	Geographic range this applies to:	Date restriction imposed:
Done	The maps are based on HydroBASINS polygons (level 06 to allow visualization), following IUCN recommendations for species from inland waters (including coastal lagoons). We used HydroBASIN polygons that overlapped with <i>R. didyma</i> records compiled from the literature.	-	-	-	Global (species is endemic to Bioregion 2).	-

Regional Assessment Map

Population

No population trends are available for *Ruppia didyma*, though it can form extensive meadows (Novelo, 1991).

Continuing Decline in Habitat

Continuing decline in area, extent and/or quality of habitat?	Qualifier	Justification
Yes	Suspected	Drainage of Guánica Lagoon in Puerto Rico. Degradation of mangroves and coastal wetlands throughout the Caribbean.

Habitats and Ecology

The ecology of *Ruppia didyma* remains poorly studied. The species occurs in hypersaline ponds in sheltered locations and clear water. It occurs in coastal lagoons dominated by the mangroves *Rhizophora mangle*, *Laguncularia racemosa*, and *Avicennia germinans*, or in ponds with *Batis maritima* and *Sesuvium portulacastrum* on the edges of mangroves (Novelo, 1991; Villarreal et al., 2014). It can occasionally co-occur with other *Ruppia* species (Novelo, 1991; Villarreal et al., 2014).

IUCN Habitats Classification Scheme

Habitat	Seas on	Suitabili ty	Major Importance?
5.14. Wetlands (inland) -> Wetlands (inland) - Permanent Saline, Brackish or Alkaline Lakes	-	Suitable	-
5.15. Wetlands (inland) -> Wetlands (inland) - Seasonal/Intermittent Saline, Brackish or Alkaline Lakes and Flats	-	Suitable	-
5.16. Wetlands (inland) -> Wetlands (inland) - Permanent Saline, Brackish or Alkaline Marshes/Pools	-	Suitable	-
5.17. Wetlands (inland) -> Wetlands (inland) - Seasonal/Intermittent Saline, Brackish or Alkaline Marshes/Pools	-	Suitable	-
9.5. Marine Neritic -> Marine Neritic - Subtidal Sandy-Mud	-	Suitable	-
9.6. Marine Neritic -> Marine Neritic - Subtidal Muddy	-	Suitable	-
9.9. Marine Neritic -> Marine Neritic - Seagrass (Submerged)	-	Suitable	-
12.7. Marine Intertidal -> Marine Intertidal - Mangrove Submerged Roots	-	Suitable	-

13.4. Marine Coastal/Supratidal -> Marine Coastal/Supratidal - Coastal Brackish/Saline Lagoons/Marine Lakes	-	Suitable	-
15.9. Artificial/Aquatic & Marine -> Artificial/Aquatic - Canals and Drainage Channels, Ditches	-	Suitable	-
15.9. Artificial/Aquatic & Marine -> Artificial/Aquatic - Salt Exploitation Sites	-	Suitable	-

Life History

Sexual reproduction in *Ruppia didyma* reportedly happens at the water surface, and the flowers are hermaphroditic (Novelo, 1991). Each inflorescence can produce up to 4 seeds, and plants can reproduce within 1 year. *Ruppia didyma* can behave as either annual or perennial (Novelo, 1991; Villarreal et al., 2014), and seeds can survive in seed banks and remain viable in habitats that become seasonally dry (Van Tussenbroek, unpublished data). Plants show limited horizontal clonal growth and tend to produce seeds very early in life (van Tussenbroek, personal observation).

Generation Length	Justification	Data Quality
1 (minimal estimate)	Annual populations complete their cycle in less than 1 year (Novelo, 1991)	-

Systems

System: Freshwater (=Inland waters), Marine

Use and Trade

General Use and Trade Information

No uses known for the species.

Threats

Ruppia didyma occupies a specific habitat, generally associated with mangrove-dominated wetlands. These wetlands are threatened by wetland degradation through land reclamation, coastal development, and pollution (Ellison & Farnsworth, 1996; Jadot, 2016; Viqueira Rios et al., 2012).

Conservation

Ruppia didyma is not directly protected but occurs within several protected areas throughout its range.

Conservation Actions In- Place

Occur in at least one PA	Note
Yes	Migrated from Conservation Measures 4.4 Habitat and Site-based actions -> Protected Areas: in-place

Research Needed

Research	Note
1.1. Research -> Taxonomy 1.2. Research -> Population size, distribution & Trends 1.3. Research -> Life history & ecology 1.5. Research -> Threats 3.1. Monitoring -> Population trends 3.4. Monitoring -> Habitat Trends	

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